

Association of Biofilm Formation and Antibiotic Susceptibility in Non-Fermentative Gram-Negative Bacteria Causing Chronic Wound Infections

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Abstract

Introduction: Non fermenting bacteria are considered as opportunistic nosocomial pathogens that are capable of causing severe chronic persistent infections. One of the main virulence factors of these bacteria is biofilm formation. Biofilms are association of planktonic bacterial cells in extra polymeric matrix. They are the most common mode of bacterial growth in nature and are also important in clinical infections.

Aim: of this prospective study was to isolate non fermenting Gram-negative bacilli (NFGNB) from wound infection, to study their biofilm forming ability along with antimicrobial susceptibility pattern. Samples were processed according to standard protocol & Tissue Culture Plate (TCP) method was used for detection of biofilm formation.

Results: A total of 400 pus samples were studied during study period. Out of these 121 (39.6%) were NFGNB. Biofilm production was seen in 55.3% isolates. It was observed antimicrobial resistance was higher in biofilm producing isolates as compared to non-biofilm producing isolates. This association was found to be statistically significant.

Conclusion: Treatment and preventive strategies for infection against pathogenic bacteria with biofilm formation is by early initiation of appropriate antimicrobial therapy, by avoiding microbial attachment to the surface, disrupting biofilm development and maturation in order to enhance antimicrobials penetration. In addition, routine testing of biofilm formation in microbiology laboratory should be encouraged for timely diagnosis and better management of such infections.

Keywords: Biofilm, Tissue culture plate method, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter* spp., antimicrobial resistance.

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Introduction

Wound infection is one of the most common infections resulting in increased mortality and morbidity among hospitalized patients worldwide.[1] Breaks in the skin along with subcutaneous tissue exposure provide appropriate moisture, temperature and nutritive conditions; facilitating microbial entry and resulting in wound infection.[2] Further, impaired host immune response, presence of debris and necrotic tissue allows bacterial attachment making wound surface ideal for biofilm formation.[3]

Biofilms are units of bacterial or fungal cells, immersed in extracellular matrix made up of hydrated polymers and debris. Biofilms formation leads to poor antibiotic penetration, nutrient limitation, slow growth and adaptive stress responses in biofilm producing microbes.[4,5] The complexity of biofilm structure and metabolism has led to the analogy of biofilms to tissues of higher organisms. It also contributes in the formation of

phenotypic variants that have resistance to antibiotics resulting in organism's survival and further dissemination in hospital setting.[1]

The usual pathogens on skin and mucosal surfaces are gram-positive cocci; however, gram-negative aerobes and anaerobic bacteria are also not uncommon.[2,6] Since most of these patients require hospitalization, there is an increasing trend of wound infection by Gram negative bacteria especially nosocomially abundant genus like *Pseudomonas* and *Acinetobacter*. [7] Both these genera are Non fermenting Gram negative bacilli (NFGNB) that are ubiquitously present on various animate and inanimate surfaces and have minimal nutrient requirements. These properties make them ideal strains inhabiting hospital environment and act as opportunistic pathogens causing various infections including wound infections.[8] Due to alarming rise in the number of infectious lesions associated by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter*

baumannii, World Health Organization declared these two bacteria on the list of 'priority pathogens' in February 2017.[9]

Research shows that *P. aeruginosa* and *A. baumannii* can survive in the presence of commonly used antibiotics, antiseptics and disinfectants, due to the presence of various enzymatic and efflux mechanisms. In addition, they also have biofilms formation capabilities which further adds to their virulence. Hence timely identification and appropriate antibiotic selection for the treatment of such biofilm associated infections is extremely important.[10]

So, this study was planned to study prevalence of NFGNB in wound infections, their biofilm forming ability along with antimicrobial susceptibility pattern.

Material and Methods

This prospective study was conducted in the department of Microbiology, Pt. BDS PGIMS, Rohtak, Haryana, India. During the study period, 400 non-repetitive pus samples collected from various types of wounds and submitted in the laboratory were processed. The study was approved by the institutional ethical committee.

Sample collection and processing

Skin was cleaned by 2% chlorhexidine and 70% alcohol. Pus was either aspirated in syringe or collected on sterile swab and sent to laboratory. Samples were subjected to Gram staining and culture. Cultures were performed on blood agar and MacConkey agar plates.

The colonies grown on the blood agar and MacConkey agar plates were processed further for the identification of the organisms by colony morphology, Gram staining and biochemical reactions as per standard microbiological protocol.[11-13]

AST were done by Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method in accordance with current CLSI guidelines.[14] The antimicrobial drugs tested were gentamicin (10µg), netilmicin (30µg), amikacin (30µg), piperacillin/tazobactam (100µg/10µg), ciprofloxacin (5µg), imipenem (10µg), meropenem (10µg), cefepime (30µg), ceftazidime (30µg) and aztreonam (30µg). An isolate was considered as Multi-Drug Resistant (MDR) if it was resistant to atleast three classes of antimicrobial agents.[15]

Biofilm production was detected by Tissue Culture Plate (TCP) method.

Tissue Culture Plate (TCP) method

This method was described by Christensen et al.[16]

Test organism was inoculated in brain heart infusion (BHI) broth with 2% sucrose dispensed in sterile test tubes and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. This broth was diluted in the ratio of 1:100 with fresh BHI broth. 200µL of this diluted culture broth was added to 96 well- flat bottom, non-adherent polystyrene tissue culture plates. Further, these tissue culture plates were incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. After incubation, the contents of the wells were decanted and wells were washed four times with phosphate buffered saline. Adhered biofilms were fixed with 2% sodium acetate for 30 minutes and stained with crystal violet (0.1% w/v) for 30 minutes.

After drying OD was taken by an automated micro ELISA reader at wavelength of 570nm. These OD values were considered as an index of bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation. Biofilm formation was considered as weak/no biofilm formation if OD value was less than 0.120, moderate if OD value was between 0.120-0.240 and strong when OD value was greater than 0.240.

Statistical Analysis

High and moderate biofilm production by each method was considered positive and weak/none biofilm production was considered negative. All the data was recorded in MS excel sheet and analyzed using SPSS software. Association of two or more set of variables was analyzed using Chi-square test. A 'p' value<0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Result

A total of 400 pus samples were studied during study period. Out of these 90 were received from burn patients, 22 from surgical site, 110 from trauma patients and remaining were other type of wound infections including venous ulcer, pressure ulcers, bed sores, osteomyelitis, diabetic foots etc. Culture positivity of these samples was found to be 76% (305 samples). Gram positive bacterial growth was obtained in 103 (34%) samples whereas Gram negative bacilli were obtained from 202 (66%) samples, of these 121 (39.6%) were NFGNB. Table 1 shows the organism wise distribution of bacterial isolates.

Table 1: Organism wise distribution of bacterial isolates

Organisms	Number	%
Gram positive bacteria	103	33.7
Enterobacterales	81	26.5
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	79	26.1
<i>Acinetobacter</i> spp.	42	13.7
Total isolates	305	

On studying their antimicrobial sensitivity pattern, the organisms were mostly sensitive to carbapenems. Imipenem was 93.6% effective in case of *P. aeruginosa* and 88.1% in case of *Acinetobacter* spp., while effectivity of meropenem was 85.7% for *Acinetobacter* spp. (96%) and 82.3% for *P. aeruginosa*. Piperacillin-tazobactam was found to be more effective against *P. aeruginosa* (84.8%) as

compared to *Acinetobacter* spp. (76%). Amongst cephalosporins susceptibility of *P. aeruginosa* was high for cefepime (53) while *Acinetobacter* spp. were mostly sensitivity to ceftazidime (54.7%). Amongst aminoglycosides, amikacin was more effective than gentamicin for both non-fermenters. Detailed antibiotic sensitivity pattern is shown in table 2.

Table 2: Antibiotic sensitivity pattern of non-fermentative Gram-negative bacteria

Antibiotics	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (n=79)		<i>Acinetobacter</i> spp. (n=42)	
	N	%	N	%
Ceftazidime	26	33	23	54.7
Gentamicin	34	43	15	35.7
Piperacillin-tazobactam	67	84.8	32	76
Amikacin	47	60	23	54.7
Aztreonam	44	55.6	22	52.4
Cefepime	42	53	11	26.2
Ciprofloxacin	34	43	11	26.2
Meropenem	65	82.3	35	85.7
Imipenem	74	93.6	37	88.1
Netilmicin	39	49.3	17	40
Doxycycline	NA	NA	23	54.8
Co-trimoxazole	NA	NA	13	30.9

Biofilm formation was studied using TCP method and biofilm production was seen in 55.3% of total isolates. Organism wise biofilm production rate is depicted in table 3.

Table 3: Organism wise biofilm production rate

Organism	Total number of isolates (n)	Number of biofilm forming isolates	Percentage (%)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	79	48	60.7
<i>Acinetobacter</i> spp.	42	19	45
Total	121	67	55.3

MDR rate was observed to be 70% for *P. aeruginosa* and 55% for *Acinetobacter* spp. A comparison of multidrug resistance was made in biofilm forming (BF) and non-biofilm forming (NBF) isolates. The association was found to be statistically significantly ($p < 0.05$). This is shown in table 4.

Table 4: Comparison of MDR among the biofilm forming and non-biofilm forming isolates

Organism	Number of BF isolates	BF MDR		Number of NBF isolates	NBF MDR		'p' value
		N	%		N	%	
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	48	39	81	31	16	51	<0.05
<i>Acinetobacter</i> spp.	19	15	79	23	9	39	<0.05
Total	67	54	80.5	54	25	46	<0.05

Discussion

NFGNB are one of the most important pathogens contributing in nosocomial infections. Their tendency to form biofilm protects them from host defense and antimicrobials further contributing to severity of infection caused by them.

They also possess inherent resistance to many routinely used antibiotics resulting into persistent chronic infections which are difficult to treat. In current study, 45% isolates of *Acinetobacter* spp. and 60.7% *P. aeruginosa* isolates showed biofilm production. Bhuvaneshwari Gunasekar et al studied NFGNB from various clinical isolates and found

biofilm production in 48 % *Acinetobacter* spp. and 49% *P. aeruginosa*, isolates.[17] Tursun MF et al found biofilm formation in 42.3% of *A. baumannii* strains and 59.5% of *P. aeruginosa* strains.[18] Nahar et al studied *Acinetobacter* spp. isolates obtained from various clinical samples and found 40% of the isolates were biofilm producers.[19] Rao et al studied *Acinetobacter* spp. isolates obtained from various clinical specimens and found 44% of the pus isolates to be biofilm producers.[20] Bala et al studied 75 clinical isolates of *Acinetobacter* spp. and reported 52% isolates as biofilm producers.[21] The rate of biofilm production was found to be comparable in the current study with these studies.

In case for *P. aeruginosa*, 60.7 % of the isolates showed biofilm production in the present study. Fatima et al found rate of biofilm production in clinical isolates of *P. aeruginosa* to be 58.3%.[22] Kaur et al studied isolates of *P. aeruginosa* obtained from various samples and found rate of biofilm production to be 58.3% in pus isolates.[23] Nithyalakshmi et al found 52% isolates of *P. aeruginosa* were positive for biofilm formation.[24] Khashaab et al studied [35] *P. aeruginosa* isolates obtained by SSI and burn wounds and observed 65.7% isolates were biofilm producers.[25]

In the present study the antimicrobial resistance pattern of the non-fermenters showed that these organisms were mostly resistant to ceftazidime, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin and co-trimoxazole. The antibiogram of *P. aeruginosa* showed 67% resistance to ceftazidime, 57% to ciprofloxacin, 47% to cefepime and 44% to aztreonam. Among aminoglycosides highest resistance was shown against gentamicin followed by netilmicin while amikacin was most effective. Carbapenems (18% resistance) and piperacillin-tazobactam (16% resistance) were most effective class of drugs. Kaur et al isolated *P. aeruginosa* from various clinical specimens and noted 78% isolates were resistant to netilmicin, 62% to cefoperazone, 57% to ceftazidime, 50% to levofloxacin, 47% to gentamicin, 40% to piperacillin, 35% to ciprofloxacin, 33% to cefepime, 17% to meropenem and amikacin.[23] In a study by Nithyalakshmi et al, *P. aeruginosa* showed resistance to ciprofloxacin (51%), ceftazidime (38%), cefepime (28.57%). Imipenem (0% resistance) and piperacillin-tazobactam (11.6% resistance) were the most effective drugs against *Pseudomonas* infections.[24]

Antibiogram by Gunasekar et al revealed 34% resistance to ciprofloxacin, 42% to ceftazidime, 40% cefepime, amikacin 12%, gentamicin 26%. Imipenem (10% resistance) and piperacillin-tazobactam (19% resistance) were the most effective drugs against *Pseudomonas* infections according to them.[17]

In our study, the antibiogram of *Acinetobacter* spp. showed 45% resistance to ceftazidime, 46% to doxycycline, 52.4% to aztreonam 69% to co-trimoxazole, 65% to gentamicin and 74% to ciprofloxacin. Imipenem (12% resistance), meropenem (14%) and piperacillin-tazobactam (24%) were most effective antibiotics. Rao et al studied 55 clinical isolates of *A. baumannii* and showed 100% resistance to imipenem, 80% to amikacin, 72.7% to ciprofloxacin, 36.3% to ceftazidime, 30.9% to cefepime and 29% to aztreonam. Cefoperazone was most effective antimicrobial drug with 91% sensitivity.[20] In a study by Bala et al the antibiogram of clinical isolates of *Acinetobacter* spp. showed 15%

resistance to piperacillin-tazobactam, 18% to imipenem, 42% to ciprofloxacin, 44% to cefepime, 46% to aztreonam and 51% to amikacin.[21]

Authors of present study found non-fermenters showing high level of resistance to commonly prescribed antibiotics like fluoroquinolones and cephalosporins. Among aminoglycosides, amikacin was found more effective while among carbapenems, imipenem had shown better activity than meropenem. Along with these drugs, piperacillin-tazobactam was found to have good effectivity against both of the organisms.

In the present study, 81% biofilm producing *P. aeruginosa* isolates were MDR while 51% non-biofilm producer showed multi drug resistance. Also, 79% biofilm producing *Acinetobacter* spp. isolates were MDR while 39 % non-biofilm producer showed multi drug resistance. This difference was found to be statistically significant showing that biofilm formation attributes in the development of multidrug resistance. Similar findings were also noted by other researchers.[17,22-24]

Conclusion

The injudicious use of antibiotics has led to development and emergence of multi drug resistant bacteria. One of the principal causes of hospital infections, the non-fermentative gram-negative bacteria escape from host defense and antibiotics by forming a biofilm, which acts as major virulence factor. With the evidence from our study, we suggest that biofilm detection should be included as routine diagnostic procedure to predict the emergence of such resistant biofilm producing isolates at the earliest. As multiple treatment approaches like anti-biofilm measures, biofilm disruption methods together with right combinations of anti-microbials are required for the management of these type of infections. Further, to control bacterial biofilm colonization/adhesion (first step of biofilm production), it is postulated to strengthen infection prevention and control strategies and antibiotic stewardship program at the health care facility. Early identification and isolation of colonized patients along with hand hygiene practices, can help to control the spread of this kind of infection.

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